

**D2.1 Strategic Vision
Statements
towards becoming
Entrepreneurial
and Innovative
Universities**

29.04.2024

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List of abbreviations

HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
ITAP	Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package

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Contact: Rimante Rusaite, rusaite@uiin.org

About the document

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Authors: Rimante Rusaite, Despoina Kortessidou, Dr. Sarah Jaber (UIIN)

Editors: Alexandra Zinovyeva, Fleur Schellekens (UIIN)

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Project Consortium

University Industry Innovation Network BV (UIIN) - Netherlands

TUM International GMBH (TUMInt) - Germany

Momentum Marketing Services Limited (MMS) - Ireland

Instituto Superior Tecnico (IST) - Portugal

Universite De La Reunion (UR) – La Reunion, France

Canarias Universidad Europea De Canarias SL (UEC) – Canary Islands, Spain

Universidade da Madeira (UMa) – Madeira, Portugal

Fachhochschule St. Polten GMBH (STPUAS) - Austria

UC Leuven (UCLL) - Belgium

Magyar Agrar- Es Elettudományi Egyetem (MATE) - Hungary

Universitatea Politehnica Timisoara (UPT) - Romania

Vidzemes Augstskola (ViA) - Latvia

In the project, the university partners are represented by or focus the project work on unique departments across their institutions. Specifically:

- UEC: School of Architecture
- UMa: *Higher School of Technology and Management*.
- STPUAS: team of Service Unit Research and Knowledge Transfer
- UCLL: Business Management and Research & Expertise
- MATE: Institute of Agricultural and Food Economics
- ViA: management team and Faculty of Society and Sciences
- IST: Department of Civil Engineering, Architecture & Environment
- UR: ESIROI engineering school
- UPT: Digital Transformation Institute - ID/IFR and e-Learning Centre

Executive Summary:

Strategic vision statements

What is this project about?

Led by [University Industry Innovation Network \(UIIN\)](#), the **Entrepreneurial & Innovative Universities Accelerator Program** (Accelerate Future HEI project) will develop and test acceleration services to equip universities with the skills and capacity to drive their institutional transformation towards becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative. The project will apply a comprehensive methodology that builds on the status quo and develops a connected vision and set of activities that provide each institution with a tailored transformation action plan.

How does this project support universities?

What is this report about?

This report presents part of the project's first year of research (Work Package 2) and specifically the nine university partners' Strategic Vision Statements (SVS) addressing the following: *"Why do we envision a more entrepreneurial and/or innovative university, what are our main goals in this desired institution, and how can we make it happen?"*

The Strategic Vision Statements of each university partner were informed by partner inputs and the activities occurring in WP2, specifically the pre-scanning, asset mapping and focus groups.

- **Pre-Scanning and Asset mapping:** an activity to identify and document the strategies, policies, and resources that can support the acceleration services at each pilot-testing university.
- **Desired Future State Focus Groups:** an activity to bring together internal stakeholders from different parts of the HEI to discuss and envision the desired future state for institutional transformation.

By analysing the outcomes of these two activities, UIIN was able to support the nine partner universities in clarifying their desired future state and goals for institutional transformation.

Below we present a **snapshot of the key SVS goals and objectives** for institutional transformation towards a more engaged, entrepreneurial, and innovative institution from each university partner.

IST's SVS goals

1. Foster internal engagement & boundary spanning
2. Cultivate external engagement
3. Recognise involvement and competence

UEC' SVS goals

1. Achieve holistic academic excellence
2. Shape innovative professionals
3. Train global and responsible citizens

UR's SVS goals

1. Commit to innovative regional development
2. Boost knowledge-driven economic growth
3. Become a multifaced hub for entrepreneurial talent

UMa's SVS goals

1. Empower tomorrow's leaders
2. Cultivate transformative higher education
3. Train tomorrow's leadership in an evolving landscape

STPUAS' SVS goals

1. Create societal impact
2. Seize market opportunities
3. Empower people and communities

UCLL's SVS goals

1. Train Moving Minds - students with an entrepreneurial mindset and skills
2. Be the catalyst for changemakers

MATE's SVS goals

1. Become the regional leader in Agriculture
2. Offer cutting-edge education for quality living
3. Promote practical sustainability through digitalisation

UPT' SVS goals

1. Strategically embrace digital evolution
2. Empower the future through digital transformation
3. Pioneering the digital future

ViA's SVS goals

1. Foster stronger engagement in local regional Innovation ecosystem
2. Drive positive change and value creation through university transformation

01

Project Overview, Aim & Approach

An overview of the project's overarching goals, objectives, methodology and consortium.

Project Overview

The **Entrepreneurial & Innovative Universities Accelerator Program** (Accelerate_FutureHEI; thereafter referred as Accelerate Future HEI) project, under the coordination of [University Industry Innovation Network \(UIIN\)](#), was launched in January 2023 and is funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe program. Accelerate Future HEI brings together **twelve European partners** from **eleven countries** to develop and implement acceleration services for institutional transformation.

Main Aim

Accelerate Future HEI aims to **develop and test acceleration services** to **equip Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) with the skills and capacity to drive their institutional transformation towards becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative**. To do that Accelerate Future HEI will apply a robust, comprehensive methodology that builds on the status quo and develops a connected vision and set of activities that provide each institution with tailored ITAPs. Participating in this initiative provides the HEIs with a unique opportunity to identify key challenges they are facing and dedicate time and resources to develop solutions through unique ITAPs.

Through this project, the HEIs are not doing this alone, but instead receive personalised and peer-to-peer guidance through access to coaches, thematic working group workshops, training workshops and cohort knowledge exchange events. This allows HEIs to take a close internal look at what they want to achieve while receiving external support and guidance to enable them to implement these changes.

Key Objectives

TO IDENTIFY

the status quo of each HEI and its ecosystem regarding entrepreneurial and innovative activities.

TO DEVELOP

test and implement acceleration services that help institutions undertake a transformation roadmap and projects

TO BUILD

the capacity of the participating HEIs' staff to implement the transformation roadmaps through **a skills development program**.

TO EVALUATE

the strategies from HEIs supervised by an 'Acceleration Board' of **independent experts**.

TO GENERATE

policy feedback to the European Commission as well as provide widespread dissemination of the pilot results to other target groups.

Project Consortium

Accelerate Future HEI brings together **twelve European partners** from **eleven countries** to develop and implement acceleration services.

Led by [University Industry Innovation Network \(UIIN\)](#), this ambitious project brings together twelve European partners from eleven countries to develop and implement acceleration services. The project consortium unites international experts on developing and supporting acceleration services, together with two established HEI consortia, one from the EIT HEI initiative (INCORE) and one from the European University Alliance (E³UDRES²) and EIT HEI Initiative (E.I.N.S). UIIN, together with TUM International and Momentum are referred to as *acceleration partners* to design and deliver the acceleration services and support the HEI *testing partners* as they implement their initiatives.

Our consortium represents institutions across Europe, including the Outermost Regions. The diversity of the partners will enable the development of overarching services that can be applied in different contexts and enable the HEIs to impact their regions.

- Testing Partners
- Acceleration Partners

Project Approach: Methodology

The project's methodology is based on a **gap analysis** which involves a **three-phase approach** to understand the context, strategy, goals and status quo of each HEI testing partner and to provide an evidence-based and solid starting point to identifying areas and opportunities for institutional transformation. The research, development and implementation phases are underpinned and supported by training, evaluation, dissemination and other activities across the project duration.

Current State Analysis

WP2 | M1 – M12

Uncovering the goals for institutional transformation.

Where are HEIs now?

The aim of this phase is to (1) clarify the desired future state and goals for institutional transformation and (2) understand the current state of each HEI testing partner and provide an evidence base for entrepreneurial and innovative activities at the partner universities. Specifically, WP2 involves activities of pre-scanning, asset mapping, focus groups, and survey. The SVS results will be explored in this report.

Developing Roadmaps & ITAPs

WP3 | M6-M18

What needs to change to achieve the goals and how will you do it?

Subsequently this phase builds on the current state data to define and design an implementation plan to achieve the desired future state and institutional transformation goals and objectives, with regards to entrepreneurial and innovative activities including the identification of opportunities and challenges to address in acceleration services and coaching activities. This will be done through the roadmap workshops as well as Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects (ITAPs).

Acceleration services pilot-testing

WP4 | M12 – M48

What will you test and implement?

This phase will support the testing partners in implementing the acceleration services and undertake actions towards institutional change, through a mixture of individual HEI and group-based support. Specifically, HEIs will undergo individual ITAP coaching with experts aligned to their core transformation focus areas, to then work on the implementation of their ITAPs and development of their investment strategy.

Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Program

WP5 | M1 – M48

HEIs will be supported with knowledge exchange and learning opportunities across the full duration of the project. In addition to the personalised coaching sessions, and the feedback, peer-to-peer feedback and mentoring guidance, which will be provided throughout *Phase 1* and *Phase 2*, HEIs will have access to dedicated events and workshops, including thematic Cohort Knowledge Exchange Events and Accelerate Training Workshops.

Acceleration Impact – Monitoring & Evaluation

WP6 | M1 – M48

The progress of the ITAPs will be tracked through a dedicated monitoring and evaluation mechanism to evaluate the impact and policy implications.

Communication and Dissemination

WP7 | M1 – M48

A communication and dissemination plan will be developed to share the transformation stories and the project's key learnings to benefit the project's community.

Management, QA & Policy Feedback

WP1 | M1 – M48

Adequate management and quality assurance processes and tools will be developed to deliver on the project's outcomes and inform policy.

Project Approach:

Foundational conceptual model

The methodology within this project is based on a combination of research and practice. One of the key models underpinning the methodology is the **UIIN Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®]** - the framework has been developed over 10 years of research and validated in practice to define the key elements of an entrepreneurial and innovative university, and the challenges and success factors associated with HEI transformation to become more entrepreneurial, innovative and engaged.

UIIN Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®]

Activities

The extent to which HEIs are innovative and entrepreneurial in their activities across education, research, valorisation and governance. This can include facilitating cooperation with surrounding research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem actors across all areas of the HEIs, and supporting the transition to knowledge- and digitally-driven HEIs that include R&I outputs in teaching.

Mindset

An understanding of the entrepreneurial and innovative mindset across leadership, academics / researchers, professional / administrative staff, and students. This focuses on fostering entrepreneurial and innovative mindsets, not only across entrepreneurial activities but across all activities to develop and nurture a problem-solving approach.

Organisational Support

The organisational mechanisms required for developing both entrepreneurial activities and mindsets within the HEI. These include: strategy and institutional commitment (e.g. HEI R&I strategies); support services and activities (e.g. mechanisms to facilitate collaboration and sharing of knowledge, capacity, infrastructure and resources) and incentives and recognition.

Impact & External Ecosystem

The external partners and supporting mechanisms in place to ensure impact pathways and the role of the HEI within its regional ecosystem. It defines the degree to which the HEIs facilitate collaboration with surrounding R&I ecosystem actors and engages citizens in solving societal challenges.

Main Deliverables

Below you can see the overview of the project’s deliverables, with the current delivered report highlighted.

Management, QA & Policy Feedback M1 – M48

The plan for how we will ensure we deliver on our outcomes & inform policy

D1.1
DMP M6

D1.2
Initial policy briefing M12

D1.3
Interim policy briefing M30

D1.4
Final policy recommendations report M48

Current State Analysis M1 – M12

Uncovering the goals for institutional transformation. Where are HEIs now?

D2.1
Strategic Vision Statements – M12

D2.2
Synthesis Report – M12

Developing Roadmaps & ITAPs M6-M18

What needs to change to achieve the goals and how will you do it?

D3.1
Roadmaps Analysis report - Draft M12

D3.2
Roadmaps Analysis report - Final M18

Acceleration services pilot-testing M12 – M48

What will you test and implement?

D4.1
Summary report - common ITAP issues M12

D4.2
Case study report- ITAPs and results M48

Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Program M1 – M48

The plan for how HEIs gain skills and insights for acceleration & transformation

D5.1
Program overview & delivery plan M12

D5.2
Program delivery progress report & updated plan M30

D5.3
Summary of the learning outcomes M48

Acceleration Impact – Monitoring & Evaluation M1 – M48

We will monitor progress and evaluate impact of ITAPs

D6.1
Monitoring & evaluation plan – M12

D6.2
ITAPs Progress report – M30

D6.3
Final Impact Report

Communication and Dissemination M1 – M48

We plan to share our key learnings so others can benefit

D7.1
Initial Plan M6

D7.2
Updated plan & first dissemination report M12

D7.3
Interim dissemination report M30

D7.4
Final dissemination report M48

02

Strategic Vision Statements: Approach

An overview of the process undertaken to define Strategic Vision Statements of each HEI testing partner.

Overview of Approach

Work Package 2 (WP2) Current State Analysis prepares the ground for development and implementation of roadmaps and ITAPs for each individual HEI testing partner.

The **aim of this WP is two-fold**: (1) to refine and articulate the vision and strategies of the testing partners regarding the desired future state of their entrepreneurship and innovation and (2) to understand the current state of each testing partner in terms of their entrepreneurial and innovation-focused activities, mindset, challenges, supporting mechanisms and activities. This is done through employing a multi-method approach of pre-scanning, asset mapping, focus group discussions, and surveys. The data gathered during this WP will provide the baseline for WP3's and WP4's development and implementation of ITAPs to accelerate the transition towards becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative university.

Pre-Scanning and Asset mapping

The purpose of this activity was to identify and document the strategies, policies, and resources that can support the acceleration services at each testing partner. The findings from this activity have influenced the focus group discussions, development of Strategic Vision Statements, and potential areas of improvement for the ITAP implementation.

Desired Future State Focus Groups

The aim of this activity was to bring together internal stakeholders from different parts of the HEI to discuss and envision the desired future state for institutional transformation. Based on pre-scanning and asset-mapping results, participants discussed goals and vision aligned with the testing partner transformation agenda and the ambition to become a more entrepreneurial and innovative university. The focus group outcomes were crucial in formulating Strategic Vision Statements for each testing partner.

Current State Survey

The primary research question being addressed through the survey is "What is the current status of external engagement, entrepreneurship and innovation at the university?" Complementing the results from pre-scanning/asset mapping and focus group discussions results, the survey collected tangible quantitative data to further ground the transformational Roadmaps for each testing partner. The survey revolved around current state of entrepreneurial and innovative activities of individual testing partners (adapting the UIIN Entrepreneurial University Framework ©) and was analysed and synthesised by UIIN. A survey report was developed and shared with each testing partner.

Defining the Strategic Vision

Statements: methodological guidelines

The elements within the SVS were informed by partner inputs and the activities occurring in WP2, specifically the **pre-scanning, asset mapping** and **focus groups**.

Step 1: Pre-Scanning and Asset Mapping

Pre-scanning

Pre-scanning involved desk research and collection of the following internal documentation at nine testing partners' HEIs including but not limited to:

- Institutional vision and mission.
- Institution-wide strategic plans and policies.
- Departmental plans and policy documentation.

Asset mapping:

The testing partners carried out an asset mapping exercise to identify and document key resources related to entrepreneurship and innovation on two levels: within their organization and within their local/regional ecosystem.

Internal (organisational) asset-mapping focuses on:

- Internal supporting mechanisms (strategies, policies, structures and activities, etc.).
- Talent/human capital (star researchers, educators, role models, leaders, etc.).
- Intellectual assets (IP, know-how, tech, inventions, programs, etc.).

External (regional/local ecosystem) asset mapping focuses on:

- Physical assets (science/technology park, incubators, accelerators, labs, production spaces, maker studios, etc.).
- Intellectual Assets (Scientific / research assets in the region).
- Human Resources (other universities,

colleges, schools, VET providers, their educational programs and experts, students and innovators).

- Network Resources (networks, consortiums, associations, key events, competitions).
- Financial Resources (regional innovation support schemes, national public funding mechanisms, private sources of funding).

Internal output: 9 Pre-Scanning and Asset Mapping documents created by each testing partner.

Step 2: Desired Future State Focus Groups

The pre-scanning & asset mapping exercise for each testing partner were followed by Desired Future State Focus Groups - guided sessions with individual testing partners around their goals and vision for institutional transformation, aligned to the transformation agenda and ambition to become an Entrepreneurial & Innovative University.

UIIN conducted guided discussions with groups of relevant stakeholders per testing partner including HEI leadership, industry and engagement, entrepreneurship, and innovation professionals working across different disciplines and areas of external engagement and entrepreneurship.

Internal output: 9 Desired Future State reports.

Duration: 2.5-3 hours

Participants: 10+

Defining the Strategic Vision

Statements: methodological guidelines

Focus groups' participants

Across the nine testing partners, 88 professionals participated in the focus groups, as shown in **Graph 1**. Academic staff, such as professors and lecturers, made up one-third of the participants (33%). Important to note, academic leadership, including deans and heads of faculties, represented 20% of the attendees. Administrative leadership, which includes coordinators and managers of university services, accounted for 14% of the focus group participation.

Focus groups' attendees across stakeholder groups

Graph 1. Distribution of survey respondents across the testing partner surveys (N=88).

Graph 2. Distribution of survey respondents across the testing partner countries (N=764). Acceleration partners (grey) did not participate in the survey.

Defining the Strategic Vision Statements: methodological guidelines

Partner	Number of participants	%
IST	10	11%
MATE	9	10%
STPUAS	9	10%
UCLL	9	10%
UEC	14	16%
UMa	13	15%
UPT	6	7%
UR	7	8%
Via	11	13%

Table 1. overview of the respondents per testing partner.

In terms of geographical distribution (**Graph 2, page 16**), an overview of the respondents per testing partner is presented in **Table 1**.

Focus group process

The focus group discussions were facilitated by UIIN team (2 facilitators in each focus group). They took place online using a collaborative canvas and covered the following topics:

- I. Reflection on current strategic orientation, transformational needs, institutional strength and opportunities.
- II. Goals, vision, mission and ambition for transformation agenda of the testing HEI.
- III. Brainstorming the desired future state for transformation in terms of activities across research, education, valorisation and/or commercialisation and management, the mindset of internal stakeholder groups, organisational support structures and commitment, and external ecosystem and impact.

Step 3: Defining strategic vision statements

In addition to the outputs of the pre-scanning, asset mapping and focus group activities, the testing partners were guided through a Strategic Vision Statement workshop, as part of the Cohort Knowledge Exchange events, where they further built on the findings to define:

- **Purpose:** Why do we want to become and entrepreneurial and innovative HEI?
- **Vision:** What do we want to achieve as an institution? What is our vision for entrepreneurial and innovative transformation?
- **Strengths:** What are our 3 key strengths and assets that will help us implement our vision?

Strategic Vision Statement Workshop

Duration: 2 hours

Participants: 25

The testing partners then consolidated the above into their strategic vision statements, which are presented in this deliverable (**Chapter 3, page 18**).

The strategic vision statements serve as the guiding light for the testing partners as they continue developing and implementing their ITAPs.

03

Strategic Vision Statements

The Strategic Vision Statements development highlighted a range of strengths across the nine HEI testing partners that will allow them to apply their ITAPs. The nine Strategic Vision Statements are presented in the following section.

Instituto Superior Tecnico (IST)

IST is the largest school of Architecture, Engineering, Science and Technology in Portugal, involving a community of over 10,000 people. By combining top quality education with research, development and innovation (RD&I) activities, according to the highest international standards, IST aims to provide students, alumni, faculty and staff an exciting and global environment geared towards solving the grand societal challenges of the century.

In the Accelerate Future HEI project, IST will be focusing on the Department of Civil Engineering, Architecture & Environment (DECivil).

Founded in
1911

1,073 faculty &
researchers

11,296
students

OUR VISION for entrepreneurial and innovative transformation

Internal engagement & boundary spanning

DECivil will be a key boundary-spanning agent at IST and the University of Lisbon, leading high-impact institutional actions that bring together different departments, research centres and existing innovation and entrepreneurship assets within the school.

External engagement & boundary spanning

Drawing on our foundations of science, technology and entrepreneurship, and our community of 1800+ boundary spanners, we will break down the siloes to connect academic, industry, government and societal stakeholders.

People involvement and competence

Our academic and non-academic staff and students will benefit from recognized and differentiated pathways to develop the skills needed to engage with internal and external stakeholders and valorise research, and adopt the mindset needed to address pressing challenges and drive collaborative innovation with real impact and outreach.

OUR STRENGTHS

Strong reputation and international standing

Capacity to develop real-time symbiotic relationships across the extended ecosystem

1800+ potential boundary-spanning entrepreneurs

Universidad Europea de Canarias (UEC)

European University of the Canary Islands also known as the UEC, is the first private higher education institution in the Canary Islands (Spain). It began its activity in October 2012, having its headquarters in the municipality of La Orotava (Tenerife). The university is integrated into the Laureate International Universities network.

In the Accelerate Future HEI project, UEC is represented by the School of Architecture.

Founded in
2012

291 faculty &
researchers

2736
students

OUR VISION for entrepreneurial and innovative transformation

Holistic academic excellence

Embodying the principles of the European Higher Education Area, we prioritize academic excellence at Universidad Europea. Our educational model goes beyond traditional approaches, focusing on providing a holistic education that nurtures maturity and autonomy in each student. We are dedicated to preparing individuals who can thrive in an increasingly complex and dynamic world.

Shaping innovative professionals

Our vision extends to shaping professionals recognized for their comprehensive set of knowledge, skills, and values. Universidad Europea students are uniquely equipped to seize enhanced employment opportunities, delivering integrated services in diverse and international settings. We foster ambition, initiative, and innovation, promoting entrepreneurship and creativity among our students.

Global and responsible citizens

At the core of our vision is the commitment to cultivate students as unique individuals who stand out for their global perspective and responsibility. We aspire to have our graduates not only excel in their respective fields of study but also emerge as global citizens, contributing positively to society.

OUR STRENGTHS

Collaborative,
entrepreneurial, determined,
and student-focused

Audacious in transforming the
traditional educational model to
enrich our students' experience

Reliable and accountable,
acting with integrity at all
levels of our organization

Université de La Réunion (UR)

9,000 km away from Europe, the University of La Réunion is the only French and European university in the heart of the Indian Ocean, in one of Europe's outermost regions. This location at the centre of the Africa-Asia-Oceania area gives it a significant role as an ambassador of higher education, research and French and European innovation in the area.

In the Accelerate Future HEI project, UR is focusing on engineering school - [ESIROI](#).

Founded in
1963

1,500 faculty &
researchers

19,200
students

OUR VISION for entrepreneurial and innovative transformation

Innovative regional development:

As the sole university in the Indian Ocean region, UR is committed to catalyzing economic and social progress. Our vision centers on fostering a culture of innovation and collaboration. We aim to contribute significantly to regional development by preparing graduates for impactful roles in the workforce and society.

Knowledge-driven economic growth

UR's mission extends beyond traditional education, emphasizing knowledge transfer and promoting graduate employability. Our aim is to participate in development by knowledge transfer and to boost the welfare by promoting the employability of graduates, and in sync with this, deepen and broaden our partnership with industry. Through this collaboration, UR evolves into a market-oriented institution, and meets the needs of the local entrepreneurial sector for industrial applicable research results.

Multifaced hub for entrepreneurial talent

Through education, research, innovation, cultural enrichment, and community engagement, we seek to have a profound impact on economic, social, and cultural aspects of society. Our overarching goal is to transform the university into an empowering force for students, enhancing internal research and development (R&D) capacity, and fostering collaboration with the entrepreneurial sector. By integrating entrepreneurship, innovation, and R&D, UR aspires to become a hub for entrepreneurial talent and industrial innovation, mutually benefiting both the university and the local entrepreneurial sector.

OUR STRENGTHS

High-impact research
potential

The university's geographical
monopoly in the Indian Ocean area

Dynamism of the local
business environment

Universidade de Madeira (UMa)

The University of Madeira is a public university in Funchal, Madeira. The university offers first, second cycle and Doctorate academic degrees in a wide range of fields, in accordance with the Bologna process.

In the Accelerate Future HEI project, UMa is represented by Higher School of Technology and Management.

Founded in
1988

300 faculty &
researchers

6000
students

OUR VISION for entrepreneurial and innovative transformation

Empowering tomorrow's leaders

Rooted in recognizing evolving needs, our purpose is to bridge the gap between traditional education and a swiftly changing world. We empower students with skills, knowledge, and a forward-thinking mindset, fostering innovation, entrepreneurial thinking, and social responsibility.

Transformative higher education

Our vision is to evolve into a forward-thinking Higher Education Institution, addressing the demands of a dynamic global landscape. By cultivating critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, and empathy alongside technological understanding, we bridge the gap between education and the job market. We are committed to equipping graduates for success in the digital age, envisioning a future where our institution thrives in change and produces leaders across diverse professions.

Leadership in an evolving landscape

Our commitment is to lead in the digital age, addressing the urgent need for reskilling and continuous learning. Envisioning graduates excelling in professions from cybersecurity to sustainability consulting, we strive to create a resilient and adaptive institution that not only embraces change but thrives in it, contributing to a more sustainable, equitable, and resilient global landscape.

OUR STRENGTHS

Young, agile and
adaptable institution

Strong representation
in the region with rich and
diverse academic environment

Commitment to interdisciplinary
collaboration, entrepreneurship and
nurturing students

Fachhochschule St. Pölten (STPUAS)

The St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences is a provider of higher education within the areas of Rail Technology & Mobility, Health Sciences, Computer Science & Security, Digital Business & Innovation, Media & Digital Technologies, and Social Sciences.

In the Accelerate Future HEI project STPUAS is represented by the team of Service Unit Research and Knowledge Transfer

Founded in
1993

435 faculty &
researchers

4,000
students

OUR VISION for entrepreneurial and innovative transformation

Creating societal impact

Our primary goal is to create added value for society, serving as a trusted partner committed to fostering an inclusive, resilient, and progressive community.

Seizing market opportunities

We actively recognize and leverage market opportunities, positioning ourselves to contribute meaningfully to societal needs.

Empowering people and communities

As a trusted partner of the European University Alliance, we are an inspirational source of knowledge transfer “in and with our communities” and the acquisition of skills for all people who care about contributing to an inclusive, resilient and progressive society.

OUR STRENGTHS

Regionally anchored and internationally connected

Interdisciplinary teaching and learning and research

Applied and challenge based research and training

UC Leuven-Limburg (UCLL)

UCLL, a member of KU Leuven Association, is a university of applied sciences that offers a unique opportunity to question the status quo and make room for innovation. We aim to maximise interaction between research and education, whilst taking our students' goals and well-being to heart by making their future our mission.

In the Accelerate Future HEI project, UCLL is represented by the Business Management and Research & Expertise teams

Founded in
2014

1,700 faculty &
researchers

16,000
students

OUR VISION for entrepreneurial and innovative transformation

UCLL is the University College of the Moving Minds

Moving Minds are inspiring, innovative and entrepreneurial professionals who, from an authentic personality and a broad, committed view of the world and their own profession, contribute to a sustainable and just society. To create Moving Minds we deliver students with an entrepreneurial mindset and skills. We conduct research and deliver services tailored to and in close collaboration with Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in the region. This way our Moving Minds contribute to a sustainable and just society.

Catalyst for changemakers

UCLL is committed to developing the region's best intra/entrepreneurial professionals, fostering a culture of pushing boundaries and driving positive change. UCLL aims to be a catalyst for "changemakers" by nurturing talented students and an engaged alumni community, empowering them to lead positive transformations in society.

OUR STRENGTHS

Embedded in the region: challenge owners, contract research and representation in business

Start Minds, UCLL's umbrella platform for entrepreneurship & and innovation

Strong link between research, education and the professional field

Magyar Agrár- és Élettudományi Egyetem (MATE)

With 5 campuses in 5 cities across Hungary, the rich history of the Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE) dates back to the 18th century. MATE stands as a central pillar of higher education in Hungary and throughout the region. We consider lessons learned from the most successful European universities and we combine our traditions with the solutions of modern ages.

In the Accelerate Future HEI project, MATE is represented by the Institute of Agricultural and Food Economics.

Founded in
2021

2,455 faculty &
researchers

13,278
students

OUR VISION for entrepreneurial and innovative transformation

Regional Leadership in Agriculture

MATE aims to become the leading agricultural-focused research university in Central and Eastern Europe. Our cutting-edge education and research aim to bridge gaps and empower diverse communities.

Cutting-edge education for quality living

MATE aims to deliver cutting-edge education and research that is driven by innovation and with a focus on enhancing the quality of life and the environment. Actively engaged in renewing higher education content, MATE aligns with international trends while prioritizing local socio-economic needs. We strive to provide relevant and accessible education that enhances opportunities for all.

Practical sustainability through digitalisation

Our efforts are geared towards promoting sustainability and a green future, while leveraging the power of digitalization. MATE believes in empowering SMEs to gain a competitive edge and shape the future of technology. Through partnerships, we contribute to a fast-paced market, ensuring our initiatives, rooted in practicality, have a tangible and positive impact on society, promoting sustainability and a green future.

OUR STRENGTHS

Multi-campus university with a strong presence in both urban and rural areas

Interdisciplinary nature across human resources, research infrastructure and collaborations

Extensive experience working with agri-food companies, clusters, and NGOs on R&D projects

Universitatea Politehnica Timișoara (UPT)

Politehnica University of Timisoara (UPT) is one of the biggest technical universities from Central and Eastern Europe. It was founded in 1920 as an answer to the need for engineers of the Romanian society in the context of the post WW1 economic recovery. During its existence, Politehnica University of Timisoara trained 131027 specialists, greatly appreciated on the national and international level for their competence.

In the Accelerate Future HEI project, UPT will be focusing on the Digital Transformation Institute - ID/IFR and e-Learning Centre.

Founded in 1920 1,000 faculty & researchers 12,500 students

OUR VISION for entrepreneurial and innovative transformation

Strategic Embrace of Digital Evolution:

UPT is committed to a comprehensive digital evolution in education and research. Starting with digitization and progressing through digitalization to digital transformation, this strategic approach has organically evolved from grassroots initiatives, guided by early adopters, and systematically implemented through university-wide policies.

Empowering the Future through Digital Transformation

UPT envisions its Digital Transformation Institute as a catalyst for digital evolution in education, research, and stakeholder engagement. With a mission to harness the full potential of digital technologies, the institute is dedicated to empowering individuals, advancing knowledge, and driving positive change in the region.

Pioneering the Digital Future

UPT's overarching vision is to be at the forefront of education, research, and regional engagement in the digital world. By empowering the future through digital transformation, the university aims to play a leading role in shaping a digitally empowered society and contributing significantly to positive change.

OUR STRENGTHS

Enablers and ambassadors of digital transformation

University-wide digital architecture and ecosystem

Connecting research, education and the community across digital transformation

Vidzemes Augstskola (ViA)

Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences is a higher education institution in Latvia. ViA promotes an entrepreneurial, inclusive, and intelligent knowledge society of the future at regional, national and international level. ViA provides full academic (bachelor, master studies) and research cycle (Ph.D. programs, postdoctoral programs, student involvement in research).

In the Accelerate Future HEI project, ViA is represented by the management team and Faculty of Society and Sciences

Founded in 1996

120 faculty & researchers

700 students

OUR VISION for entrepreneurial and innovative transformation

Fostering stronger engagement in local regional Innovation ecosystem

ViA's aim is to contribute to the resilience and growth of future society by being relevant and sustainable and by being involved in the international community. This will promote sustainable business and digital transformation, help industry produce products and services with higher added value, provide research, data insights and analysis for future needs, support development of human capital, and encourage students and staff entrepreneurship

Driving positive change and value creation through university transformation

We prioritise cultivating an entrepreneurial mindset among students and alumni, equipping them with critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, creativity, digital skills, and risk-taking acumen. We advocate for a lifelong learning mindset, emphasising inclusivity and technological advancement. To bolster our transformation, we actively seek increased research funding and industry partnerships, supporting research projects, infrastructure development, and overall university advancement.

OUR STRENGTHS

Dynamic environment, ambitious, flexible and able to quickly make changes and adapt

Access to eternal assets and openness to new ideas

Connected projects and active scientific activity in regional, national and international scale research

04

Conclusion

Reflection on the role Strategic Vision Statement play in developing and testing acceleration services for HEIs

Conclusion

Strategic Vision Statements play a crucial role within the Accelerate Future HEI methodology as they are the foundation behind the goals for transformation. Below, key reflections on the strategic vision statements are captured below, based on the experiences of the testing partners, in relation to the broader objective of developing and testing acceleration services for HEIs transformation:

Alignment with institutional transformation goals

Strategic vision statements articulate the long-term goals and aspirations of the nine testing partners. In the context of HEIs, these statements help align the acceleration services with the overarching objectives of institutional transformation.

Informing roadmaps and implementation projects (ITAPs)

The methodology builds on the existing initiatives and strengths of each testing partner, and emphasises understanding the current state and desired future state of each testing partner. Strategic vision statements provide a clear direction for ITAPs by guiding what the testing partners aim to achieve in terms of entrepreneurial and innovative activities.

Defining focus areas and core transformation objectives

Vision statements highlight key focus areas and core values. These statements guide the identification of opportunities and challenges that need to be addressed in the acceleration services. This ensures that the designed services are tailored to the unique goals and values of each HEI.

Ownership and buy-in:

Strategic vision statements contribute to ownership and internal buy-in. When HEIs

actively participate in crafting their vision statements, they develop a sense of ownership. This ownership is crucial for the success of acceleration services, as institutions are more likely to commit to and invest in strategies that align with their vision.

Communication and knowledge exchange:

Vision statements serve as communication tools, both internally and externally. They help convey the institution's commitment to transformation. During knowledge exchange events and workshops (as mentioned in the methodology), strategic vision statements provide a context for sharing insights and learning from others.

Monitoring and evaluation:

When testing acceleration services, strategic vision statements can become benchmarks for evaluating success through setting clear metrics. They provide criteria against which the impact of services can be measured, ensuring that the transformation aligns with the institution's strategic direction.

Adaptability and responsiveness:

As institutions evolve, vision statements may be revisited. This adaptability is important, especially during the pilot-testing phase. Strategic vision statements guide the flexibility needed in adjusting acceleration services based on the evolving needs and goals of HEIs.

In summary, strategic vision statements serve as foundational elements that guide the entire process of designing and testing acceleration services. They were further used to ground the discussion of the roadmap workshops as part of WP3, and will continue to provide guidance for the testing partners as they develop their ITAPs to plan, test and evaluate institutional transformation within the context of the testing partners.

Follow our journey

To learn more, visit the project www.acceleratefuturehei.eu

Contact Us

Rimante Rusaite
 Senior Project Officer- UIIN
 E-mail: rusaite@uiin.org
 Web: <https://www.uiin.org/>

supporting future focused higher education

